

1 **Wound healing and regeneration pathways are engaged during TNBC resistance.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
Amphiregulin (*AREG*) and epiregulin (*EREG*) were activated following exposure to a chemotherapeutic agent in TNBC cells. Sirtuin *SIRT4* was activated, as were other nicotinamide metabolic pathway genes.

9 Citation

10 1. Shoyab, M., Plowman, G.D., McDonald, V.L., Bradley, J.G. and Todaro, G.J., 1989. Structure and
11 function of human amphiregulin: a member of the epidermal growth factor family. *Science*, 243(4894),
12 pp.1074-1076.

13 2. Zaiss, D.M., Van Loosdregt, J., Gorlani, A., Bekker, C.P., Gröne, A., Sibilia, M., en Henegouwen,
14 P.M.V.B., Roovers, R.C., Coffey, P.J. and Sijts, A.J., 2013. Amphiregulin enhances regulatory T
15 cell-suppressive function via the epidermal growth factor receptor. *Immunity*, 38(2), pp.275-284.

16 3. Shirakata, Y., Komurasaki, T., Toyoda, H., Hanakawa, Y., Yamasaki, K., Tokumaru, S., Sayama, K.
17 and Hashimoto, K., 2000. Epiregulin, a novel member of the epidermal growth factor family, is an
18 autocrine growth factor in normal human keratinocytes. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 275(8),
19 pp.5748-5753.

20 4. Laurent, G., German, N.J., Saha, A.K., de Boer, V.C., Davies, M., Koves, T.R., Dephoure, N.,
21 Fischer, F., Boanca, G., Vaitheesvaran, B. and Lovitch, S.B., 2013. SIRT4 coordinates the balance
22 between lipid synthesis and catabolism by repressing malonyl CoA decarboxylase. *Molecular cell*, 50(5),
23 pp.686-698.

24 5. Anderson, K.A., Huynh, F.K., Fisher-Wellman, K., Stuart, J.D., Peterson, B.S., Douros, J.D.,
25 Wagner, G.R., Thompson, J.W., Madsen, A.S., Green, M.F. and Sivley, R.M., 2017. SIRT4 is a lysine
26 deacylase that controls leucine metabolism and insulin secretion. *Cell metabolism*, 25(4), pp.838-855.

27 6. Csibi, A., Fendt, S.M., Li, C., Poulogiannis, G., Choo, A.Y., Chapski, D.J., Jeong, S.M., Dempsey,
28 J.M., Parkhitko, A., Morrison, T. and Henske, E.P., 2013. The mTORC1 pathway stimulates glutamine
metabolism and cell proliferation by repressing SIRT4. *Cell*, 153(4), pp.840-854.

7. Haigis, M.C., Mostoslavsky, R., Haigis, K.M., Fahie, K., Christodoulou, D.C., Murphy, A.J.,
Valenzuela, D.M., Yancopoulos, G.D., Karow, M., Blander, G. and Wolberger, C., 2006. SIRT4 inhibits
glutamate dehydrogenase and opposes the effects of calorie restriction in pancreatic β cells. *Cell*, 126(5),
pp.941-954.